

Kinetic and mechanistic study of oxidation of cystine by hexacyanoferrate(III) ions catalyzed by Ir^{III} in aqueous alkaline medium

Anjali Goel* and Savita Gupta

Department of Chemistry, Kanya Gurukul Mahavidyalaya, Gurukul Kangri University, Hardwar-249 407, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : goelanjali@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The iridium(III) catalyzed hexacyanoferrate(III) (abbreviated HCF(III)) oxidation of cystine in aqueous alkaline medium has been investigated spectrophotometrically. The reaction is found first order in oxidant, catalyst and alkali concentration while with substrate concentration reaction follows Michaelis-Menten type kinetics. Positive salt effect was observed by using the potassium chloride solution. Different activation parameters were also evaluated by studying the reaction at four different temperatures. The stoichiometry of the reaction was found 1 : 8 of reductant and oxidant. A suitable mechanism has been proposed to explain all the experimental results. It is assumed that reaction proceeds through complex formation between substrate (abbreviated S) and iridium trichloride. A rate law has been derived which verifies the results.

Keywords : Iridium(III), hexacyanoferrate(III), cystine, oxidation.

Introduction

The oxidation of amino acids is of utmost importance both from the chemical point of view and from its bearing on the mechanism of amino acid metabolism. The study of oxidation of cystine has become important because of its biological significance and selectivity towards the oxidants¹⁻¹⁰. In the present study the detailed kinetic study of hitherto unstudied catalytic activity of Ir^{III} in the oxidation of cystine in aqueous alkaline medium by HCF(III) has been carried out.

Results and discussion

The iridium(III) catalyzed oxidation of cystine has been studied in aqueous alkaline medium. Kinetic experiments were comes out at different concentrations of one reactant keeping the concentrations of others constant.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by estimating the amount of HCF(II) ions produced after definite interval of time with standard solution of ceric(IV) sulphate using ferroin as redox indicator¹¹. Eight stoichiometry was observed between HCF(III) and amino acids. Spectroscopic and chromatographic method¹² are used to identify the oxidation product after 24 h. The oxidation

product cysteic acid was confirmed by TLC using the solvent water saturated phenol. The presence of sulphonic acid group was confirmed by IR spectra of the products -SO₃ (sulphonic group) asymmetric stretching at 1188.15 cm⁻¹ and for -OH (sulphonic group) stretching at 2921.84 cm⁻¹.

The kinetic results reveal that oxidation of above said amino acid follows first order kinetics with respect to HCF(III). The concentration of HCF(III) was varied from 2×10^{-4} to 6×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. The initial rates were calculated by plotting absorbance vs time plots (Table 1). The straight line plots plotted between initial rates in terms of $[(dA/dt)]_i$ vs concentration of HCF(III) confirms the first order kinetics with respect to HCF(III).

To study the effect of substrate concentration on reaction rate, the substrate concentration has been varied from 0.1×10^{-4} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. First order dependence of rate on lower concentration of substrate tends to be zero order at its higher concentration (Table 1). The linear plots of rate^{-1} vs $[S]^{-1}$ suggest Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics (Fig. 2).

Increase in rate with hydroxide ion concentration reveals first order kinetics with respect to hydroxide ion

Table 1. Effect of [HCF(III)], [Cystine], [NaOH] and [Ir^{III}] on the reaction rate at the temperature 35 °C and ionic strength 0.5 mol dm⁻³ of reaction mixture

[HCF(III)] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Cystine] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[NaOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Ir ^{III}] × 10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	[dA/dt] _i × 10 ³ (min ⁻¹)
2.00	3.00	0.4	3.35	1.2
3.00	3.00	0.4	3.35	1.8
4.00	3.00	0.4	3.35	2.6
5.00	3.00	0.4	3.35	3.4
6.00	3.00	0.4	3.35	4.00
3.00	0.1	0.4	3.35	0.6
3.00	0.2	0.4	3.35	1.2
3.00	0.3	0.4	3.35	1.6
3.00	0.4	0.4	3.35	2.2
3.00	0.5	0.4	3.35	2.6
3.00	0.6	0.4	3.35	3.2
3.00	0.7	0.4	3.35	3.6
3.00	0.8	0.4	3.35	4.00
3.00	0.9	0.4	3.35	4.00
3.00	1.00	0.4	3.35	4.00
3.00	3.00	0.1	3.35	1.2
3.00	3.00	0.2	3.35	2.4
3.00	3.00	0.3	3.35	3.4
3.00	3.00	0.4	3.35	4.4
3.00	3.00	0.4	0.335	0.4
3.00	3.00	0.4	0.67	0.8
3.00	3.00	0.4	1.01	1.2
3.00	3.00	0.4	1.34	1.6
3.00	3.00	0.4	1.67	1.8
3.00	3.00	0.4	2.01	2.4
3.00	3.00	0.4	2.34	2.6
3.00	3.00	0.4	2.68	3.00
3.00	3.00	0.4	3.01	3.4
3.00	3.00	0.4	3.35	3.8

concentration. The concentration has been varied from 0.1–0.4 mol dm⁻³. The reaction rate also increases with the catalyst concentration indicating a direct dependence of rate on catalyst concentration. The concentration of iridium was varied from 0.335 × 10⁻⁵ to 3.35 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ (Table 1).

Effect of ionic strength was studied by using KCl. The linear increase in log (-dc/dt) with $\sqrt{\mu}$ suggest the positive salt effect i.e. the involvement of two similarly charged reacting species in the reaction (Fig. 3).

Activation parameter :

Thermodynamic parameters of the reaction were stud-

ied at four different temperatures 35, 40, 45 and 50 °C under pseudo-first order conditions. Activation parameters were evaluated from linear Arrhenius plots. The value of energy of activation (E_a) is 54.48 joules/moles, enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) 51.85 joules/moles (ΔS^\ddagger) and free energy of activation (ΔF^\ddagger) 84.51 joules/moles respectively.

Reacting species of iridium :

In case of 3rd transition series, elements of higher states are more stable. It is reported¹³⁻¹⁷ that in hydrochloric acid medium IrCl₆³⁻ is the stable species. It does not give divalent complex. The stable species are Ir³⁺

Fig. 1. Plots between absorbance and time for the variation of [HCF(III)] in the oxidation of cystine. [Cystine] = $3.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [NaOH] = 0.4 mol dm^{-3} , [Ir^{III}] = $3.35 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = $35 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 420 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 2

and Ir¹⁺. The aquation of IrCl₆³⁻ give IrCl₅(H₂O)₂, IrCl₄(H₂O)₂¹⁻ and IrCl₃(H₂O)₃ species as shown in the following equation :

Since no retarding effect of Cl⁻ ions was observed, the hydrated species can't be the reactive species. Only [IrCl₆³⁻] has been considered as the only reactive spe-

Fig. 3. Effect of ionic strength on the rate of oxidation of cystine. [HCF(III)] = $3.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [Cystine] = $3.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [NaOH] = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} , [Ir^{III}] = $3.35 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = $35 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 420 \text{ nm}$.

cies. Sheila *et al.*¹⁶ also reported IrCl₆³⁻ as the reactive species in oxidation reaction.

Mechanism :

Cystine is a dimer of cysteine. The disulphide bond is readily reduced to the corresponding thiol (-SH). It is reported by Annapurna *et al.*¹⁹ that the oxidation of cystine yields cysteic acid more frequently.

In the mechanism it is assumed that organic substrate form a loosely bonded complex (C₁) with Ir³⁺ which slowly reacts with HCF(III) ions resulting into Ir¹⁺, HCF(II) and intermediate product (IP). Ir¹⁺ is reoxidised to Ir³⁺ by two moles of HCF(III) via one electron transfer process and the IP disproportionates to final product.

The rate of reaction can be given as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{HCF(III)}]}{dt} = k_2[\text{C}_1][\text{HCF(III)}]$$

According to above mechanism the rate of disappearance of HCF(III) can be given as

$$\frac{-d[\text{HCF(III)}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 K[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{HCF(III)}][\text{Ir}^{3+}]_T}{k_{-1} + k_2[\text{HCF(III)}] + k_1 K[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (1)$$

At very low concentration of HCF(III) ions and organic substrate the value of $k_2[\text{HCF(III)}]$ and $k_1 K[\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]$ will

be quite small. Hence neglecting these factors eq. (1) reduces to

$$r = \frac{k_1 k_2 K [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{HCF(III)}] [\text{Ir}^{3+}]_T}{k_{-1}} \quad (2)$$

$$r = k k_2 K [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{HCF(III)}] [\text{Ir}^{3+}]_T$$

$$\text{where } k = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}}$$

The rate law eq. (2) clearly accounts for the first order kinetics with respect to HCF(III), organic substrate, hydroxide ion and the catalyst at their lower concentration.

The validity of rate law might be ensured by rewriting the eq. (1) as follows

$$\frac{1}{r} = \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2 K [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{HCF(III)}] [\text{Ir}^{3+}]_T} + \frac{1}{k_1 K [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] [\text{Ir}^{3+}]_T} + \frac{1}{k_2 [\text{HCF(III)}] [\text{Ir}^{3+}]_T}$$

The straight line plots between 1/rate vs 1/HCF(III) and 1/rate vs 1/cystine proves the validity of above rate law. The value of k_2 and $k_1 K$ has been calculated from the intercept of 1/rate vs 1/HCF(III) and 1/rate vs 1/cystine plots (4.15×10^{-5} and $2.62 \times 10^6 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively). The constancy in $k_1 K$ and k_2 clearly shows the validity of derived rate law equation on the basis of proposed mechanism.

Experimental

The kinetic experiments were carried out by mixing the required quantity of cystine solution maintained at constant temperature with solution of HCF(III), sodium hydroxide, potassium chloride and iridium(III) chloride kept at the same temperature. The solution of cystine was prepared by dissolving a weighed quantity in 0.25 M solution of NaOH. The concentration of HCF(III) was not kept more than 6×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. All experiments were carried out in thermostatic water bath at constant temperature 35 ± 0.1 °C and ionic strength 0.5 mol dm⁻³. Potassium chloride was used to keep the ionic strength constant. The progress of the reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} 420 nm and there was no shift in λ_{\max} during the entire period of kinetic study. Plane mirror and Guggenheim methods were used for evaluation of initial rates $(dA/dt)_i$ and pseudo-first order rate constant k_1 respectively. Spectroscopic and TLC methods were used to identify the oxidation products.

References

1. Kirk Othmer, "Ency. Chem. Tech. , Vol. 2, 4th ed., p. 556.
2. Iftikhar Ahmad and C. Muhammad Ashraf, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2004, 11, 813.
3. Niranjan Nalwaya, Anju Jain and B. L. Hiran, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, 79, 587.
4. D. C. Hiremath, K. T. Sirsalmath and S. T. Nandibewoor, *Catal. Lett.*, 2008, 122, 144.
5. P. K. Satpathy, G. C. Dash, S. Acharya and P. Mohanty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, 83, 891.
6. K. Sharanabasamma, Mahantesh A. Angadi, Manjalee S. Salunke and Suresh M. Tuwar. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2009, 48, 10381.
7. Timy P. Jose, Sharnappa T. Nandibewoor and Suresh M. Tuwar, *J. Sulphur Chem.*, 2006, 27, 25.
8. Timy P. Jose, Sharnappa T. Nandibewoor and Suresh M. Tuwar, *J. Sol. Chem.*, 2006, 35, 51.
9. Anjali Goel, Shakunj and Shivani, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2008, 6, 1891.
10. Timy P. Jose and Suresh M. Tuwar, *J. Mol. Structure*, 2007, 827, 137.
11. J. N. Bronsted and W. F. K. Wynne-Jones, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 59.
12. J. Richard and L. Emmett, "A Manual of Paper Chromatography and Paper Electrophoresis", 2nd ed., Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1958.
13. J. C. Chang and C. S. Garner, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 209.
14. F. A. Cotton and Wilkinson, "Adv. Inorg. Chem." Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1976, 434.
15. J. D. Lee, *Concise Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 209.
16. Y. I. Kravtsov, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem. (Eng. Trans.)*, 1964, 9, 552.
17. I. A. Poulsen and C. S. Garner, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 2032.
18. Sheila Srivastava and Vandana Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, 83, 1103.
19. N. Annapurna, A. Kalyan Kumar, P. Vani and G. Nageswara Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, 85, 542.

